

Roscas and Their Impact on the Development of Small Businesses in Sierra Leone. (Case Study-Gbongo Market-Bo)

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Abstract

Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (RoSCAs) are a micro-credit scheme that enables low-income groups to access financial services. RoSCAs are informal financial institutions that serve many people's financial needs, especially in developing countries. There is an increasing need for RoSCAs, especially among small business owners, as they provide an alternative to raise funds to support their business operations since this group would typically face difficulties obtaining financing from the formal banking sector. This study examined the impact of RoSCAs on the development of small businesses in the Gbongo market, Bo City-Southern Sierra Leone. This study applied a mixed research design and explored primary and secondary data sources. A well-designed questionnaire was administered to 120 small business owners, who were selected using a simple random sampling technique in addition to the focus group discussions held with the heads of those schemes in the market area. The ensuing data was analyzed using simple statistical packages like Excel and frequency counts, and the result was presented in charts. This study found that the practice of RoSCAs has served as a mechanism for savings, provides capital with less strings attached, strengthens networks, helps to accumulate assets and eventually alleviates financial exclusion by enhancing the involvement of small business owners in financial activities and economic development. Therefore, it would be necessary for policymakers to integrate RoSCAs in the economic policies for the pivotal role they play in economic development, improving financial inclusion and hence aiding in poverty reduction.

Keywords: RoSCA, Osusu, Development, Small Businesses, Sierra Leone

1. INTRODUCTION

RoSCAs, which stands for Rotating Savings and Credit Associations, are formally organized groups of people who join together to save and lend money. All members contribute a predetermined amount at a predetermined time, and each member takes the contribution in turn. RoSCAs encompass a group of individuals who meet within a defined period to save and borrow.

According to Bouman (1983) [1], RoSCAs are the poor man's bank where money changes hands routinely, and all parties involved are satisfied. They carry different nomenclatures in different places around the world. For instance, they are also known as 'Tandas' in Latin America, Partnerhand in the West Indies, Ajo in Nigeria, Susu in the Caribbean and West Africa, Hui in Asia, and so on (Dalia, 2024) [2].

RoSCAs are universal and take many forms, but they most often consist of individuals who contribute regularly to a fund given to each member in rotation. For example, six people may agree to give ten thousand USD to fund every month for six months. Each month, a different group member collects sixty thousand USD, which each of the other five members contributes and uses for their business expenses or personal consumption. This arrangement allows people with a low socio-economic status to access such resources. RoSCAs carry different names in different countries. Given the lack of external regulations and the incentive for RoSCA members to stop contributing after their turn to collect, it is remarkable how the default rate is among Rotating Savings and credit associations worldwide.

Biggart (2001)[3] believes that the success of RoSCAs can be attributed to the following:

- A communally based social order
- Obligations that are held to be collective
- Social and economic stability
- Social and economic Isolation
- Similarity among RoSCA members in social status

From a system of exchange perspective, RoSCAs are primarily a commercial system. They exist only with social groups that bond through kinship ties, clan membership, or common identity with a geographic location. Furthermore, they only rely on those social ties to ensure reasonable behaviour (as in “[3]”).

The researchers are convinced that on a Continental basis, RoSCAs are arguably the world’s most elegant, most efficient and most reliable informal financial device, capable at their best of transforming the economies of a whole community. The RoSCA reputation is on the rise just as micro-credit is tottering. After a spectacular crash in India and serious difficulties elsewhere, microcredit has sometimes been accused fairly of harmful practices, harsh collection practices and price gauging, which have produced the dark side of microfinance. RoSCAs are immune to these ills. The money they circulate comes from the members, not from outside, guaranteeing that the volumes involved are manageable by the users. Not all RoSCAs charge for their loans, but when they do, the members and returns set the price as interest on their savings. RoSCA users are not pressured into borrowing, over-indebtedness is rare, and price gauging and losing resources to outsiders do not happen. This has helped small-scale business owners because it gives them the free will to engage in their businesses while being a member of RoSCA. The idea that outsiders have no ownership of their resources gives them the urge to take the RoSCA with all seriousness.

The New York Times ran a story about RoSCAs users in some parts of the world earning themselves formal credit source: Kim Wilson at Tufts University told the New York Times a banker who awarded an immigrant family a mortgage after reviewing their success in making RoSCAs payment. There are online RoSCAs in India, too; a researcher from Ithala College notes that in India, 'RoSCAs remain strong despite greater financial inclusion'. Similar studies find the same. (Jim Wilson-New York Times 2014) [4]

In West Africa, RoSCAs have reached a level where people appreciate it to the extent that they rely on it for their business and family. Some people use it as a way of saving their money. People fear that if they save their money on their own, they might be tempted to use it, so RoSCAs has solved that problem for them. The individuals in RoSCAs select each other, ensuring participation is based on trust, social forces, and genuine commitment. RoSCAs are informal or pre-co-operative microfinance groups that have been documented around the developing world. Moreover, the first credit union in Africa was in Northern Ghana in 1955 by the Ghanaian Catholic Missionaries. However, susu, which is one of the finance schemes in Ghana, is known to have started in Nigeria and spread to other West African countries, including Sierra Leone, in the early 20th century (Nsoh, 2016) [5]

RoSCAs have become the layman's bank in Sub-Saharan Africa (West Africa). This is because of the high poverty level in these countries; Sierra Leone is no exception. These people use RoSCAs to save what they have. They use what they get from the RoSCAs to set up businesses or to make some materials available to their families. In so doing, RoSCAs have been of massive help to people in West Africa, including Sierra Leone.

Sierra Leone started the Osusu as early as the 20th century, spreading throughout the nation. The inhabitants of this nation (Sierra Leone) were predominantly engaged in Micro microfinance loans, which are loans given to farmers and business people on an interest basis. Because of the interest levied on farmers and business people, which sometimes landed them in jail, they decided to form the Osusu, where interests were not paid on the contributions a person received. Hence, the Osusu, as a branch of a microfinance institution in Sierra Leone, came into existence and is now practised nationwide.

In Sierra Leone, some groups have done it through Orange Money to simplify the RoSCAs. They do this by sending the Orange Money to the individual who collects it from other members. For instance, Christian Aid Sierra Leone designed a project they called “The Women Economic Empowerment and Leadership” project for Pujehun and Kailahun in the Eastern part of Sierra Leone, which was mainly designed to strengthen and transform existing savings and credit schemes in both Districts through the use of the Orange-Money and RokelSimkopor platforms that were already in existence (Christian et al., 2023) [6].

The idea was that they saw RoSCAs as an effective and efficient medium for succeeding in their business ventures. The group is supposed to help its members, who are primarily women, with easy access to interest-free loans (as in “[2]”).

Moreover, the idea of RoSCAs has also helped traders handle basic family needs, including the payment of school fees and university fees, among others, and engage in activities that otherwise cannot be accomplished by a single individual. Therefore, it is generally accepted that RoSCAs have been very effective in the socio-economic well-being of ordinary citizens. However, this study explicitly targets how the RoSCAs have helped develop small businesses in the Gbongo market.

2. RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Background and importance of RoSCAs to small businesses and households

Ajija and Siddiqui (2021) [7], declared that a RoSCA is an organization of self-selected persons. Participants in the RoSCA usually share the same network, which can be the same neighbourhood, workplace, religious, or ethnic group. Although RoSCAs operate with slight differences, they follow the same basic framework. Usually, a group leader organizes among friends, neighbours, workmates, or relatives to form the association.

Abeyrathna (2024) [8], in describing the RoSCA, refers to it as a mutual help network. People in the group set an amount of money, and each member contributes weekly or monthly. The members gather and work using a cyclical method with different names. Some groups meet monthly, and members are expected to make their contributions. The lump sum collected is given to a designated member whose turn is to collect. When all the members have received the lump sum at least once, depending on the entry at the beginning of the scheme, the RoSCAs can either dissolve or restart the cycle (Ahn et al., 2016 [9]; Gugerty, 2007 [10]; Nelson, 1995 [11]). RoSCAs provide a specific quantum of capital to its members and offer some security and credit on a tiny scale, services that are not common amongst most financial institutions (Mbizi&Gwangwava, 2013 [12]; (as in “[11]”). RoSCAs also provide social support through group meetings for their members. These groups have been a source of community support for fragile households to cope with specific crises through networks of informal and formal relationships.

Clement (2022) [13], observed that using RoSCAs significantly impacts S.M.E.'s access to capital in the Western Region of Cameroon. It follows logically that S.M.E.s in that region should use such associations more to improve their access to finances. There is a correlation between RoSCAs membership and operations sustainability. (as in “[12]”). Lasagna and Lollo (2011) [14] reported that the endowment of social capital at the village level positively correlated with Rosca's participation in Indonesia. Also in Nigeria, Adebajo (2010) [15], noted that ROSCAs have brought relief to the people because it is very convenient and easy to access funds, especially so when, despite several efforts by various governments and international bodies through very lofty programs, poverty persists at an alarming rate in most of Africa. Kabuya (2015) [16] also mentioned a critical reflection on using RoSCAs to reduce poverty in local communities. The authors found that RoSCAs make a significant difference in the welfare of its members and small business owners, and they are measured as a change in household consumption.

2.2 Categorization of RoSCAs and Rationale for their formation

Ademola et al. (2020) [17], examined the justification for joining RoSCAs, and they found that the financial motive supersedes all other motives among the majority of the respondents that participate in RoSCAs to obtain loans for investing in their businesses, as well as pay school fees and handle other domestic

challenges. Other motives, such as insurance and commitment, were mentioned, as members stressed that RoSCAs help nurture proper saving habits and create an easy way to obtain funds. Their findings showed that RoSCAs' participation is highly influential because it serves as a means for saving, provides capital with fewer attachments, improves relations, and helps accumulate assets.

Gelinas (1998) [18], categorizes the RoSCAs in the market into three types: investment RoSCAs, bidding RoSCAs and marketplace RoSCAs.

The professional RoSCA runner who collects contributions from the market and then disburses them to the members rotatably organizes the marketplace RoSCA, which is prevalent in most underdeveloped societies. The organizer usually reserves their commission for their services, and the remaining proceeds are distributed among members. Although the three types of RoSCAs are run in the market, only investment RoSCAs are widely used by entrepreneurs as part of their business.

The majority of people in the study area are low-income or average-income earners. As a result, they cannot save huge sums at the bank. The solution to such a problem is RoSCA, as it is the only way they can put a small sum together and give it to one of their members.

Moreover, the RoSCA also provides credit facilities for its members, which they invariably use to add to their capital to help improve their business. By so doing, the RoSCA has helped provide more capital for small business owners.

The insurance motive is another contended suggestion as to why members join RoSCAs. It stressed those RoSCA members who do not necessarily want to take the pot early since the RoSCAs are insurance schemes. Members who have not received the pot yet and suddenly need some money because of an emergency could take RoSCAs as insurance. However, this only works when other members, including the next pot winner, are willing to reverse the order (Sandor, 2010) [19]. A criticism against the insurance mechanism is that people grouped in a given RoSCA often have similar backgrounds in terms of location, culture, and revenue. This contrasts with risk-sharing activities against idiosyncratic shocks.

Furthermore, there is the "Social Pressure model", which assumes that individuals cannot resist the day-to-day pressure from society. Hence, they use RoSCA to escape from pressures (Ambech & Treich, 2003) [20]. Another reason people might want to join RoSCAs and tie themselves with some saving style is their awareness of their procrastinating nature- the feeling that they can start saving anytime. Thus, they need some commitment device to cope with such challenges. This marks the point of departure for (as in "[10]"), in developing the commitment device model, which he believed is a commitment mechanism for individuals who do not have access to suitable commitment technologies. Commitment mechanisms do have two essential features: the deposit feature and the withdrawal side features (Ashraf, 2006) [21]. The deposit side feature helps in regular periodic deposits, as opposed to the features on the withdrawal side, which discourage or deter withdrawals.

Finally, Addo, P. A. (2017). [22], argued that some individuals wish to join RoSCAs because of an intra-household conflict. According to them, the household maximizes the utilization of limited income, which often leads to conflict in terms of budget allocation. This scenario affects men differently as opposed to women. Men often concern themselves more about consumption in a household, while women are believed to be careful about having durable goods and consumption in the household. Thus, women use RoSCAs as a means to solve such conflicts. Women sometimes even join RoSCAs without their husbands' knowledge. However, Dagnelie and Lemay-Boucher (2008) [23], challenged the "household conflict motive" in their study in Benin. 40% of the sample group in their study requires spouse approval to become a member. RoSCAs, known as Osusu in the study area, are usually formed to save money for those without a huge sum to save at the bank. Members of RoSCAs usually make their daily, weekly, or monthly contributions to their heads. The money collected by the head is given to the person to collect at that time. Members use the money collected to increase their capital. This has encouraged most of the traders in the market to have encouraging capital for their small businesses.

Apart from the business reason behind the formation of RoSCAs in most communities, members of the RoSCAs use the money collected for other purposes. They can use the money collected to finance the schooling of their children. Because some traders cannot take a considerable amount of their capital to finance schooling, they turn to RoSCAs as a solution to that problem.

They can also use the money they get from RoSCAs to purchase household materials for their homes. They usually do this to maintain their little capital.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Description of study area

Bo is an ethnically diverse city in Sierra Leone. It is home to a significant population of many of the Country's ethnic groups. However, the Mende people form the largest ethnic group in the city, even though Krio is the most widely spoken language in Bo city.

This study was conducted in the Gbongo market, where the researchers elicited the primary data. Gbongo market is the third most significant and busiest market in Bo City. According to the Bo City Council Table Registration Report 2023, Bo City has 3,482 registered business tables covering eight market centres. Of these tables, Gbongo Market accounts for 406 registered small businesses.

However, despite the significant contribution of this market to the community and city at large, access to finance for the sustainability and expansion of their business has been a severe challenge. Compared to others in the central part of the city, this market has a limited number of nearby commercial banks or existing microfinance institutions. Even where they are present, the red tape and other bottlenecks they pose make them hard to reach. This limited number of on-lending firms in the community, among many other factors, serves as a deterrent for many business owners to expand their business scale, especially those who may not want to source funds outside the community either as a result of distance or personal reasons, which have forced these owners to resort to RoSCAs as the significant scheme to save and lend rotationally.

Most of the small business owners in this market are women, with makeshifts and tables as the primary holding units of their businesses (see Fig. 1 below). Others peddle with theirs in baskets and trays. The most common items sold here are food items, with some nearby shops with building materials and other businesses.

Figure 1: Makeshifts and food items displayed by market women at the Gbongo market in Bo City.
Source: Field Survey, 2024

3.2 Techniques

A mixed research design was used for this study, and both primary and secondary data sources were used. A well-designed questionnaire was administered to small business owners, who were selected using a simple random sampling technique. Additionally, focus group discussions were held among RoSCA operatives, especially the heads of those schemes in the market area. A total of 120 respondents were selected for the study. The ensuing data was analyzed using simple statistical packages like Excel and frequency counts, and the result was presented in charts.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.1 Prevalence of RoSCAs in Study Area

The concept of RoSCAs or Isuzu is familiar to the target population for this study. For most petty traders, 74.1%, Osusu is the most common source of funding for their businesses and the most common informal financial institution. The study further shows a massive involvement, 93% of business people in the RoSCA scheme. The reasons for the high participation in this scheme are outlined in Fig. 2 below.

Figure 2: Main reasons for choosing RoSCAs by petty traders. Source: Field Survey 2024

4.2 Effect of RoSCAs on Other Financial Institutions

Although other microfinance institutions exist in the city, such as Sierra Leone Micro Finance, Finance Salone, Brac Micro Finance, and many more, the flexibility and other advantageous characteristics of RoSCAs serve as a better alternative for petty traders in this area. According to the study, this has been a challenge for the smooth running of other financial institutions. On the other hand, small businesses consider RoSCAs an essential means through which they can start up their businesses, enhance their abilities to save and handle other expenses like paying school fees for their wards and purchasing valuable items for themselves.

However, this phenomenon does not suggest that participants of this scheme do not encounter problems in their affairs. Figure 3 below illustrates some significant challenges these informal financial institutions face.

Figure 3: Problems Encountered by RoSCA Members
Source: Field Survey 2024

5. SUMMARY

ROSCAs or Osusu were considered the most common funding source for most petty traders, and most traders, 93%, were involved in the scheme. The less bureaucratic processes and absence of interest rates involved, in addition to other benefits, are the reasons for the high involvement of business people in the scheme.

Furthermore, to a certain degree, ROSCAs and their flexibility have constrained the chances for some financial institutions to target small businesses in the area. Nonetheless, members of the RoSCA scheme also encounter a series of challenges in their schemes' operations. Key among these challenges is the seizure of some members to contribute their quota just after receiving their lots and the lateness in payment of contributions by some members.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the study, the emergence and practice of ROSCAs have a tremendously positive impact on the development of small businesses. The scheme has been a significant source of funding for small businesses. Nevertheless, the informality and lack of discipline among the members are severe challenges to the smooth running of ROSCAs. Finally, the degree of involvement of petty traders in ROSCAs suggests that ROSCAs are the best alternatives to other financial institutions for funding their business and handling other household financial matters.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made for the effective and efficient functioning of ROSCAs

- ✚ Proper background checks on the membership of the RoSCA are crucial for an effective and efficient scheme.
- ✚ Local authorities acting as arbitrators in the operation of ROSCAs can give them some legitimacy, which will discourage bad behaviour.
- ✚ Proper care must be taken to select the head of the scheme.
- ✚ Since the practice of ROSCAs can boost the economy (according to the research findings), duty bearers (central and local government) should establish social legislation to aid the effective, regular, stable and efficient operation of ROSCAs without losing sight of the flexibility that attracts local business owners to the scheme.

- ✚ Policymakers in the economic sector should include informal financial institutions, especially RoSCAs, in their economic policies because of their pivotal role in economic development and, hence, aiding in poverty alleviation.
- ✚ Donor agencies and N.G.O.s that want to improve the lives of petty traders should use RoSCAs as a tool or medium, as this will enhance the attainability of their goal.
- ✚ Key actors should create advocacy commissions or institutions to ensure the smooth running of RoSCAs in the study area and the nation.

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